

When interacting with AI, make me think

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Synopsis

We report work in progress that examines the neurophysiological and perceptual effects upon users of a Generative AI tool developed to serve as a general assistant within an enterprise, helping to perform various administrative tasks. Participants interacted with the AI tool in three ways: chatbot, chatbot plus summary, or chatbot plus form, with an additional manual control task. We compared neurophysiological and perceptual responses across tasks and, more broadly, across AI interaction modalities. We performed time-frequency decomposition to derive power estimates in the delta, theta, alpha, beta and gamma frequencies for all tasks and interaction modalities, producing t-maps to illustrate the differences in brain activity. Our findings illustrate that interacting with AI requires varying degrees of cognitive effort compared to manually performing tasks. However, the dynamics of this brain activity are nuanced and vary significantly across interaction modalities, as do perceptions.

Background

In the rapidly evolving landscape of artificial intelligence, recent developments have expanded the AI toolkit to include conversational agents, natural language processing, and machine learning for automating administrative tasks, allowing users to focus on more cognitive tasks while automating repetitive tasks, leading to increased productivity. In the last year alone, these tools have converged into multipurpose, generative pre-trained transformers (GPTs). These GPTs are large language models (LLMs) utilising transformers to combine large multimodal data sets and immense computing power to create an intelligent model which, after training, can generate complex, advanced, human-level output (Vaswani et al., 2017) in the form of text, images voice and video. These models are capable of multi-round human-computer dialogues, continuously responding with novel output each time users input a new prompt due to having been trained with data from the available corpus of human knowledge, ranging from the physical and natural sciences through medicine to psychiatry. Furthermore, these models now possess the capability of performing actions giving them agentic properties (Dwivedi et al., 2023), useful for a host of tasks within industry and the workplace.

However, downstream of these sunlit uplands lie the effects on the users of these AI-based systems which remain largely unknown. It is these unknowns that motivate this study to answer the question *“to what extent does interacting with an AI assistant to perform business tasks impact the cognitive and emotional state of users, and perceptions towards AI assistants?”*

Methods

Participants $n=31$, aged 19 – 44 ($\mu = 29$, 15 female), were taken from our institution’s panel of Business School participants. Participants were screened based on good health, average hair density, normal or corrected to normal vision, and knowledge of business organisations. All participants provided signed consent in line with the university’s research ethics committee.

The stimuli (see Figure 1) used in this study were developed by our industrial partner and represent an in-development ecologically valid generative AI assistant based on a foundation LLM. That is, the AI assistant was developed in-house using a pre-trained LLM that was later optimised for a specific industrial purpose. The assistant interacted with participants in real-time to complete three tasks, in one of three ways: Mi-1 chatbot, Mi-2 chatbot & summary and Mi-3 chatbot & form.

A standard (International 10-20 system) montage 32-electrode EEG (Brainvision, Morrisville, NC) was utilised to measure variations in brain activity. Data were captured at 1000 Hz and subject to bandpass filtering (0.5-50Hz) and moderate artefact detection and removal using ICA ($\mu = 2$ components). A Hilbert transform was applied to these data to derive time-frequency amplitudes in the Δ (0.5-4Hz), θ (4-8Hz), α (8-12Hz), β (15-30Hz) and γ (30-49Hz) frequency bands. Additional pupillometry measures and perceptions of agency, confidence and trust were captured.

Results

Preliminary analyses were performed in *brainstorm* (Tadel et al., 2011), using non-parametric, independent samples permutation t-tests (Monte-Carlo $rnd=1000$). We found significant differences ($p < 0.05$, FDR corrected) in time-frequency envelopes across a range of frequencies when comparing control with all AI interaction modalities for the same task (See Figure 2).

Such that, Mi-2 was shown to induce more complex patterns of brain activity, compared to the other modalities or control. Additionally, significant differences in frequency dynamics were found between the three AI interaction modalities, both within task one and more broadly across all three tasks.

In terms of perceptual measures, we found that participants reported their sense of agency was largely unaffected by interaction with the AI. However, participants did report a higher sense of agency when using Mi-2, compared with other modalities or control. Furthermore, participants also reported that confidence and trust in the AI tool, regardless of interaction modality was high compared to control.

Discussion

Overreliance on AI (Vasconcelos et al., 2023), loss of agency (Legaspi et al., 2024), leading to relinquished responsibility (Ahmad et al., 2023) are predicted to become a major concerns as AI technology continues to develop. Our preliminary results show surprising neural activity dynamics across AI interaction modalities compared with control. Specifically, the range of activity during Mi-2 points toward the creation of set of design and development principles that lead to creating and inserting a form of induced intentional friction in the interactions between human and AI that allows for additional reflection, engagement of critical thinking and action responsibility. This concept of induced intentional friction flies in the face of years of human computer interaction practice, which has focused on creating frictionless interactions as a form of added value. When fully realised the results of this study have the potential to significantly impact our understanding of AI's effects on users and how best to design collaborative human-AI working practices.

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